

CLASSICA

Validating AI in classifying cancer in real-time surgery

Training report

Document date: 9 January 2024

Document version: 1.2

Deliverable No: D3.1

Dissemination Level: Public

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Executive Summary

The Horizon Europe CLASSICA project aims to clinically validate an AI-based technology for identifying and analysing cancer tumours. Validation will be carried out across several clinical sites, surgical teams, and countries.

Tumour tissue has significantly different vasculature from healthy tissue, and irregular angiogenesis is a hallmark of tumour development. In CLASSICA, our technology uses rapid analysis of tissue fluorescence dynamics to differentiate between cancerous and non-cancerous tissues. In essence, the fluorescence intensity of pixels displaying tissues of interest varies with blood flow (perfusion) when the blood is dyed with fluorescent indocyanine green (ICG) and lit by near-infrared (NIR) light. The fluorescence intensity (FI) is captured over time from multiple video frames and plotted as a curve. The intensity curves of tumour tissue differ from those of healthy tissue, and those of benign tumours differ from malignant ones. Analysis of the curve features for each pixel in a region of interest can thus lead to a classification.

This deliverable is an output of Task 3.1 ‘Create Training Resources’ and Task 3.2 ‘Deliver training’. It describes the training video and training delivered to date. As the software being validated in this project is deployed within a clinical method, the first component of training was to develop and standardise the clinical protocol between the collaborating clinical centres.

The Study 1 protocol was broken down into a step-by-step process to create the first training video, guiding surgeons at each clinical site. Emphasis was placed on avoiding disruption to the surgical workflow and identifying pitfalls during video acquisition.

In the process of creating the training video, several clinical sites contributed their first transanal surgery video recordings. Pitfalls related to the adjustment of the NIR camera position during recording were identified and underscored in the video, using clinical cases as illustrative examples. Given the inverse correlation between FI and distance, any inadvertent camera movements had the potential to alter the obtained perfusion curves.

All clinical sites (UCD, UNITO, ZOL, VUmc, BBGRAZ) and our technology partner (Arctur) required training in the standardised performance of this clinical method, while the legal and bioethical partners (UCPH, PSU) required training in basic principles of surgical performance regarding this technique. For the first phase of the CLASSICA, and while the software is being advanced to clinical grade for real-time trialling, the video imagery obtained needs to be uploaded to a specific web-based portal, allowing for annotation and inclusion of pseudoanonymous clinical metadata, which also used for clinical investigator training. Training for Study 1 is now complete and sets the scene for the next stage of training with our AI software.

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List of acronyms, definitions and abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CRC	Colorectal Cancer
DTIF	Disruptive Technologies Innovation Fund
DoA	Description of Action
FI	Fluorescence intensity
FOV	Field of View
ICG	Indocyanine Green
NIR	Near-infrared
OP	Operating Procedure
OR	Operating Room
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction to CLASSICA

CLASSICA will deliver and clinically validate an artificial intelligence (AI)-based decision support technology, which enables rapid identification of the presence and distribution of rectal cancer tumours. Clinical validation will be carried out across several institutions, surgical teams, and countries.

The technology uses rapid analysis of tissue fluorescence dynamics to differentiate between cancerous and non-cancerous tissues. It has been applied in the context of colorectal cancer (CRC) surgery and transanal surgery and has demonstrated excellent accuracy in differentiating between cancerous and healthy tissue [1]. Essentially, the fluorescence intensity (FI) of pixels displaying tissues of interest varies with blood flow (perfusion) when a commercially available fluorescent dye named indocyanine green (ICG) is systemically administered and excited using a near-infrared (NIR) light. The FI is then captured over time from multiple video frames, and this intensity is plotted as a curve. Intensity curves for tumour tissue are different from those of healthy tissue, and those of benign tumours are different from malignant tumours. Analysis of the curve features for each pixel in a region of interest can subsequently lead to an AI-based classification.

The specific objectives of the project are to:

- Deploy and perform clinical validation studies across five clinical sites, located in Ireland, Belgium, Austria, Italy, and the Netherlands.
- Assess the usability, safety, and performance of the CLASSICA system.
- Agree upon standard operating protocols for the implementation and use of the CLASSICA system.
- Develop and deliver training for the use of CLASSICA tissue classification tools during biopsy and surgery.
- Develop new guidelines to help guide the use of AI for surgical decision support.

The project builds on breakthrough research by the Irish DTIF Consortium comprising UCD, RCSI, and IBM Research, which developed the novel research premise which will be optimised and validated in the CLASSICA project.

1.2 Training resources

As the CLASSICA software being validated in this project is deployed within a clinical method, the first step in creating training resources involved developing and standardising the clinical protocol among the collaborating clinical centres. Key training steps are outlined in WP3, focusing on the following objectives:

- Create training resources for Studies 1, 2, and 3
- Train surgeons and OR staff in each clinical site
- Work with training recipients to further improve training resources

This deliverable, 'D3.1 Training report' outlines the results from Task 3.1 'Create Training Resources' and Task 3.2 'Deliver training'.

2 Training Resources

The study method involves the administration of an approved dye to a patient undergoing an examination of their anorectum under general anaesthetic. The area of interest needs to be observed transanally using an existing, commercially available endoscope (PINPOINT, Stryker) for five minutes, and the imagery so obtained is recorded. In the context of training, CLASSICA clinical and technical partners (UCD, UNITO, ZOL, VUmc, BBGRAZ, Arctur) required training in the standardised performance of this clinical method, while the legal and bioethical partners required training in basic principles of surgical performance regarding this technique.

CLASSICA Study 1 is a prospective, unblinded, multicenter observational study validating the use of ICG with AI analytics to differentiate areas of cancer vs areas of non-cancer within a rectal polyp. For the first phase of the study, and while the software is being advanced to clinical grade for real-time trialling, the video imagery obtained is uploaded to a specific web-based portal (CLASSICA-Web). This allows for annotation and inclusion of pseudoanonymous clinical metadata, and also facilitates clinical investigator training. Study 1 training has been successfully conducted by UCD and IRCAD, in collaboration with our clinical partners and Arctur. We are now poised to enter the next training phase, focusing on deploying the AI software in surgery for Studies 2 and 3. This will involve using our software in the operating room (OR) during surgery (CLASSICA-OR).

2.1 Create Training Resources

As part of the CLASSICA project, we are transforming the clinical trial protocols from Studies 1, 2, and 3 into practical resources to facilitate their implementation in the OR. These resources include training videos, presentations, and documented standard operating procedures (SOPs). SOPs are used to create a step-wise training resource. Our efforts to date have concentrated on Study 1. Notably, this involved translating the Study 1 protocol into an accessible, step-by-step guide (Figure 1 below illustrates the opening screen of the first training video).

Under Task 3.1, IRCAD and UCD have successfully completed the training of clinical partners for Study 1. This includes the creation of a comprehensive training resource for investigators and other potential users. This training has standardised the method for acquiring surgical video of ICG-perfusion patterns in patients. The ongoing mathematical analysis and comparison of these videos with those from previous studies are crucial for validating the generalisability of the AI assessments across different clinical sites. The Study 1 protocol is available in deliverable D2.1 *“Final Clinical Validation Protocol, Patient Information Document, Consent Forms”*, with the final text as approved by Mater Hospital ethics committee available in D4.7 *“Study Initiation Package”*.

Figure 1 Introductory part of the CLASSICA training video featuring representations of all partners' logos

Surgical standardisation techniques for video acquisition in Study 1: It is imperative that the surgical technique and peri-operative preparations conform with local standard procedures and individual surgeon preferences. However, to ensure the validity of our results, certain steps need to be standardised across all procedures. Steps such as bowel preparation, lesion visualisation, camera stabilisation, video recording and clinical scenarios where two tumours were identified, were agreed upon and documented across all clinical sites.

The **profusion checklist**, represented in Figure 2, serves as a verification tool and is structured around two main components: preoperative preparation and the operating procedure (OP). Preoperative preparation focuses on key tasks related to the PINPOINT optical imaging system and guidelines for ICG preparation, while the OP covers essential surgical aspects. In combination with the surgical standardisation technique, the checklist not only guided Study 1 at each clinical site but also contributed substantially to the creation of the CLASSICA training video.

OP checklist for using the PIN-POINT system

Preparation:

- Preparing the trolley with the pin point
- Cabling with the monitor and the central storage system (Christopher Kauc)
- Sterile: light cable, camera head, camera probe
- ICG-Verdye: 0.25 mg/kg (e.g. patient with 100kg receives 25 mg Verdye/body weight : 4) Dissolution with water for injection - anaesthesia

OP start

- Insertion of the rectal gel port
- Insufflation with Airseal to 14-15 mmHg (depending on arrangement)
- Visualisation of the lesion
- Washing out the rectum with saline solution (please do not use BI due to discolouration)
- Adjusting the camera to the lesion
- **Start the video recording** (hold the camera very still!)
- Insert an endoscopic instrument with a diameter of 5 mm for 2-3 seconds, then remove it again (only used to determine the size)
- i.v. application of ICG
- Video continues to run for at least 5 minutes after ICG injection
- Stop recording
- OP is carried out as planned
- Saving the video to the USB stick

Figure 2 OP checklist for using the PINPOINT system

Training video: The foundation for developing this step-by-step training resource was laid by the Study 1 protocol, which details the treatment of study subjects. The training video presents a standardised clinical approach for capturing surgical footage of ICG-perfusion patterns during transanal surgery. Essential discussions on techniques for optimal video acquisition occurred during the CLASSICA plenary meeting held in Nova Gorica on the 10th and 11th of November 2022. During this event, clinical partners showcased videos demonstrating their current transanal surgery methods and identified potential pitfalls relevant to the CLASSICA project. Insights gathered from these discussions, both on-site and online, played a crucial role in defining the initial video content.

In March 2023, IRCAD shared an initial version of the training video. Valuable feedback from surgeons collected during the video presentation at the CLASSICA plenary meeting held in Amsterdam on the 22nd and 23rd of May 2023 was essential for refining the content. Throughout the creation of the

training video, several clinical sites contributed with their initial transanal surgery video recordings. The final version, which integrates surgeon feedback and enhancements, was subsequently released as part of our Study 1 protocol article published in Colorectal Disease.[2].

The CLASSICA training video for Study 1 provides crucial information, including the ICG dose, the precise timing for initiating video acquisition in near-infrared (NIR) mode, and the total duration required when recording video (Figure 3).

Figure 3 ICG dose and total length of video acquisition for the CLASSICA Study 1

The video emphasises and tackles challenges associated with adjusting the position of the NIR camera during recording, using clinical cases as illustrative examples. It highlights the inverse correlation between FI and camera distance. Given that any unintentional camera movements could alter distance, impacting the acquired perfusion curves, it is imperative to avoid any movements once recording (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Video capture representing a NIR camera movement during the acquisition, areas highlighted in purple represent rectal tissue that was not shown at the beginning

In addition, the training video provides a thorough examination of potential clinical scenarios, offering guidance on how to navigate them. This includes dealing with easily accessible and small polyps, those with bleeding or oozing, and large polyps (Figure 5).

Figure 5 Potential clinical scenarios represented within the CLASSICA training video

The postoperative analysis specifics are discussed in the video, specifying that data analysis for this study will be carried out at UCD. Video recordings, follow-up data, and histopathological reports will be uploaded via the CLASSICA-Web platform in Study 1 (with CLASSICA-OR available for Study 2). The AI-decision support system will then provide quantification and ICG kinetics over time, ultimately providing a probability assessment of the lesion being cancerous or non-cancerous (Figure 6).

Figure 6 Postoperative analysis planned for the Study 1

Towards the end of the video, an overview highlighting crucial factors for high-quality video acquisition is provided. These include minimising camera movement, ensuring an accurate representation of the rectal polyp and normal mucosa, minimising blood in the field of view (FOV), and preventing any movement of instruments during the recording (Figure 7).

Figure 7 Summary outlining the key elements for producing a high-quality video acquisition

In conclusion, this training video **details the standardised clinical method for capturing surgical video of ICG-perfusion to enable pattern analysis and AI representation in patients**. Preliminary insights from CLASSICA Study 1 are promising, showing that the AI's assessment of video footage is consistent across all clinical sites, mirroring the results previously achieved in Dublin. In addition to obtaining video footage for AI training and development, the surgical technique plays a crucial role in applying the AI software, given that its utilisation follows the administration and observation of ICG. Therefore, such training will allow surgeons to be familiar with video requirements for the future clinical studies.

2.2 Deliver training

Delivering training involves providing instruction to both clinical and technical CLASSICA partners. The clinical partner training commenced with an initial session during the CLASSICA kick-off meeting in Dublin in 2022 (Figure 8), offering in-person presentations, open discussions, and peer-to-peer learning. This included video presentations of existing techniques, addressing questions, and exploring case-based scenarios aligned with the DoA. A subsequent training session at the end of 2022 (Figure 9) focused on optimising video acquisition through a "tips and tricks" session and video demonstrations illustrating optimal and suboptimal practices. The outcomes from both training sessions laid the groundwork for creating the first training video (Task 3.1) to prepare surgeons for Study 1.

Figure 8 CLASSICA Coordinator Prof. Cahill in-person presentation at the project kick-off 9th May 2022

In January 2023, UCD led targeted training through partner conference calls, offering personalised sessions designed to meet the specific needs of each clinical partner. Finally, in-person training during the third CLASSICA plenary meeting in Amsterdam in May 2023 covered foundational aspects and further refined the training process.

Figure 9 Video demonstration during Nova Gorica plenary meeting 10th November 2022

Regarding technical partner training, Arctur's technical team actively participated in the training sessions held during the kick-off and plenary meetings. In June 2022, Arctur visited the Mater Hospital

(UCD) operating theatre. This visit played a crucial role in familiarising the WP1 team with surgical OR communication and the fundamental aspects of surgical workflow. The first-hand experience proved essential for identifying potential challenges in deploying CLASSICA-OR. In addition, this on-site field training offered valuable insights to enhance the implementation of CLASSICA-OR in Studies 2 and 3.

During January 2023, clinical partner standardisation meetings were conducted via conference calls. UCD independently hosted these meetings with clinical investigator at each centre, providing site-specific training to ensure standardisation across all clinical sites. Such meetings allowed for protocol standardisation and agreement, considering the centres' practices regarding transanal surgery procedures.

In addition, UCD facilitated the NIR optical imaging system (Stryker PINPOINT) setup at each clinical site (Figure 10). Considering that all clinical partners are experienced colorectal surgeons proficient in laparoscopic and endoscopic surgery, the training on the PINPOINT system focused on theatre staff familiarity as well as software and button activation mode by the clinical teams.

Figure 10 Stryker PINPOINT optical imaging system used in CLASSICA

In January 2023, Stryker product manager and UCD provided tailored training for the clinical partner BBGRAZ, as this site was unfamiliar with the Stryker device (Figure 11).

Figure 11 PINPOINT training hosted by Stryker Austria at BBGRAZ on 18th January 2023

Each of the five clinical partners (UCD, UNITO, ZOL, VUmc, BBGRAZ) have conducted pilot cases for Study 1. These involved testing the PINPOINT device within the OR to evaluate its use during transanal surgery and ensure adherence to the surgical standardisation techniques outlined in Task 3.1. Such pilot cases have testified to the correct use of the NIR optical imaging system as specified in the Study 1 protocol. Three clinical sites have recruited patients and effectively used the system to create appropriate surgical video imagery for computational analysis.

Figure 12 Validation of the PINPOINT optical imaging system in the OR on the 7th and 10th Feb. 2023 at two subjects, including video recording of 5 min according to the Study 1 protocol

Since the training also considers a broader surgical community, IRCAD and UCD plan to host a **CLASSICA webinar** in the upcoming months. This free IRCAD CLASSICA webinar will focus on the integration of AI and fluorescence-guided surgery in the treatment of colorectal cancer. In addition, relevant topics such as legal dimensions of AI decision support systems will be addressed. This online educational event aims to provide solid evidence of the advantages AI-driven surgical support offers to both patients and surgeons. The session will be recorded and subsequently uploaded to [WebSurg](#), IRCAD'S online University platform, to facilitate wider access.

3 Impact & Conclusion

Training initiatives for Study 1 have been successfully executed, as the training video for Study 1 has been created and published in a high impact surgical journal. Such publication allows broader dissemination within the surgical community. In addition, training has been delivered to all clinical and technical CLASSICA partners. Importantly, the training video and delivered training have been crucial in standardising the capture of ICG-perfusion patterns across clinical sites.

By standardising the video acquisition process in the CLASSICA project, we significantly enhance the reliability of our analyses and ensure data comparability across various sites. Such consistency is vital for validating AI assessments in surgical environments. Through the training video, we not only provide an essential training tool but also showcase the project's potential impact to a broader audience.

Key achievements so far include:

- ✓ Creation of training resources, including documented SOPs and instructional video.
- ✓ Development and publication of a comprehensive training video for Study 1, detailing the standardised clinical method for ICG-perfusion pattern acquisition.
- ✓ Successful publication of the training video as part of the CLASSICA Study Protocol journal article.
- ✓ Delivery of training in the clinical method of Study 1, establishing the basic field for the use of CLASSICA-OR in actual human surgery.

Looking ahead, our training will focus on equipping surgeons and OR staff at each clinical site with the skills to use the CLASSICA AI system in real-time surgeries. These training resources, including slide decks and updated SOPs will be instrumental in supporting the clinical validation for Studies 2 and 3. They will guide surgeons in using CLASSICA-OR intraoperatively for biopsy and resection procedures using simulated and observed cases. Our commitment to continual development and training underlines our dedication to surgical practices with AI technology, ultimately improving patient care and surgical outcomes.

References

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